

FAUNA AND DYNAMICS OF TICKS TRANSMITTING BOVINE THEILERIOSIS IN THE NORTHERN REGIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Abstract. The article examines the fauna and dynamics of ticks that transmit bovine theileriosis in the northern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Ticks were collected from a total of 90 cattle infested with ticks: Chimbay district (30 head), Bo‘zatov district (30 head), and Nukus district (30 head). The tick species *H. anatolicum* and *H. detritum* were identified. Tick identification was carried out using the method of B.I. Pomerantsev (1950), while species names and classification followed the identification guides developed by N.A. Filippova (1997). When studying the tick fauna transmitting the causative agent of theileriosis in the northern regions, it was found that *H. anatolicum* accounted for 76.6% in Nukus district, and *H. detritum* reached up to 53.3% in Chimbay district. Cattle infestation with ticks was observed in May and June, with infestation intensity reaching 210 and 180 specimens, respectively.

Keywords: tick, theileriosis, region, imago, pathogen, pasture, host, *H. anatolicum*, *H. detritum*.

Introduction. Over the past decade, a large proportion of land areas has remained untilled, which has led to drought conditions and an increase in pasturelands. At the same time, a reduction in the volume of treatments with acaricidal preparations has contributed to an increase in the population of ixodid ticks. These ticks, in turn, have found favorable conditions for continuing their biological development cycles.

Along with this, these dynamics, as part of eco-biological changes, have influenced the acceleration of disease spread. The reduction of acaricidal treatments and the decline in agrotechnical services in the regions have facilitated the spread of theileriosis and other parasitic diseases. In recent years, these changes have led to a deterioration of the epizootic situation and the widespread occurrence of infectious diseases among cattle.

Based on epizootic analyses, it is shown that deep plowing of land areas and the implementation of acaricidal treatments are of great importance in disease prevention. Therefore, the effective implementation of agrotechnical and preventive measures plays a significant role in improving the epizootic situation.

According to the authors, mass attacks of ixodid ticks cause significant losses to animals, namely: a decrease in body condition, weakening of the immune system, the appearance of allergic reactions, and, in cases where a large number of ticks feed simultaneously on the host animal’s body, they may even lead to the death of the animal [1; pp. 29–31; 4; pp. 186–191; 5; p. 16; 6; p. 304].

In addition, information is provided on the occurrence, under the conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, of *H. detritum* and *H. anatolicum* ticks, which act as carriers of the causative agent of bovine theileriosis and have a certain level of epizootological significance [2; pp. 422–444; 3; pp. 14–16].

Materials and Methods. Studies on the fauna of ticks transmitting blood-parasitic diseases of cattle were conducted during the summer season on cattle from farm enterprises in the Nukus, Chimbay,

and Bo‘zatov districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In order to determine the distribution dynamics of ticks and their epidemiological role in the northern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, ticks were collected and analyzed from 90 head of cattle (30 animals from each farm) in three districts. Tick identification was carried out according to the method of B.I. Pomerantsev (1950).

Results and Discussion. To determine the reasons for the spread of theileriosis in different climatic zones, special attention was paid to the role of ixodid ticks as vectors of blood parasites. Climatic conditions and differences between geographical zones can directly influence tick abundance and activity, which in turn is an important factor in shaping the epidemiological situation of diseases.

Ixodid ticks transmitting the causative agent of bovine theileriosis were collected from the Nukus, Chimbay, and Bo‘zatov districts. Ticks were mainly collected in areas with a high incidence of the disease, on pastures where animals were grazed, and from farms where cases of theileriosis had been recorded. In addition, cattle yards, pastures, exercise areas, as well as places where animals stayed and rested during the day were inspected to determine the presence or absence of ticks.

During the observation period, it was established that the attachment of hungry ticks to the animal body mainly began in April, when the average air temperature rose to 10–15 °C. The peak periods of tick attacks on cattle on pastures were recorded mainly in the morning from 6:00 to 10:00 and in the evening from 17:00 to 21:00. During the study, the fauna of ticks transmitting blood-parasitic diseases of cattle in the northern regions of the Republic was determined (Table 1).

Table 1
Fauna of ticks transmitting blood-parasitic diseases of cattle in the northern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

No.	Name of farm	Number of cattle examined (head)	<i>H. anatolicum</i>		<i>H. detritum</i>	
			(n), head	%	(n), head	%
1	Nukus district, “Qo‘ng‘rotboy-Mehri” farm	30	23	76.6	7	23.3
2	Bo‘zatov district, “Shahamanly Asadbek” farm	30	18	60.0	12	40.0
3	Chimbay district, “G‘arezsizlik” farm	30	14	46.6	16	53.3
	Total	90	55	61.2	35	38.8

According to the results of the analysis, the most widely distributed species were identified as *H. anatolicum* and *H. detritum*. No specimens of *V. calcaratus* were found. During the study, data on the degree of tick infestation and the intensity of invasion in cattle are presented in the table.

Based on the indicators shown in the above table, it was established during the study that tick infestation in cattle was mainly concentrated on the fore and hind limbs, around the anal region, and in the udder area, where infestation levels were the highest.

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In order to determine the seasonal dynamics of ixodid tick infestation in cattle, 30 head of cattle were examined monthly (Table 2). Tick infestation in cattle was observed in May and June, with invasion intensity reaching 210 and 180 specimens, respectively.

Table 2
Seasonal dynamics of tick infestation in cattle

Months	Number of cattle (head)	Tick infestation		Intensity of invasion (specimens/head)
		head	%	
January	30	0	0	-
February	30	0	0	-
March	30	13	43,3	26
April	30	28	93,3	90
May	30	30	100	210
June	30	30	100	180
July	30	30	100	150
August	30	25	83,3	46
September	30	22	73,3	20
October	30	8	26,6	12
November	30	0	-	-
December	30	0	-	-

The high number of the tick population in cattle during certain months (Figure 1) is associated with favorable environmental conditions and with violations of the timing of treatments using insecticidal preparations.

Figure 1. Seasonal dynamics of tick infestation in cattle.

The periods during which ixodid ticks parasitize cattle may vary depending on climatic conditions.

According to the table and figure above, in the northern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, tick parasitism on cattle begins in spring, starting from March, when adult ticks (imago) become active and ticks that have molted from nymphs to adults start parasitizing cattle. The tick population increases and reaches its peak in May and June.

Hyalomma anatolicum and *Hyalomma detritum* ticks are considered vectors of the causative agent of theileriosis. These tick species are found along watercourses and lake shores, in moist livestock pastures, in areas covered with shrub vegetation, and in livestock complexes. Thus, in the northern districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, *H. anatolicum* and *H. detritum* are the most widely distributed tick species. Their distribution range in different climatic zones varies depending on weather and climatic conditions.

It was also observed that ticks use vegetation cover as protection from the negative effects of direct sunlight. In addition, a certain association between specific plant species and ticks of the species *Hyalomma anatolicum* and *Hyalomma detritum* was identified. In particular, ticks preferentially use plants such as camelthorn (*Alhagi*), reed (*Phragmites*), and licorice (*Glycyrrhiza*) as shelters.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the conducted study, ticks of the species *Hyalomma anatolicum* and *Hyalomma detritum*, which parasitize cattle and act as vectors of the causative agent of theileriosis, are widespread in the northern districts of the Republic. The attachment of hungry ticks to the animal body mainly begins in April, when the average air temperature rises to 10–15 °C. During the study, it was established that tick attacks on cattle on pastures occur mainly in the morning from 6:00 to 10:00 and in the evening from 17:00 to 21:00. An increase in tick abundance was observed in May and June.

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